

CHARACTERIZING PIEZO-FILM SENSOR FOR DIRECT VIBRATION AND IMPACT MEASUREMENT

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with characterizing piezo-film sensor to determine the dynamic response of $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4]_s$ laminate made of s-glass/epoxy pre-preg (Fiberite, HY-E 9134B). The simple plate- and beam-type sensor equations are derived based on the classical plate theory with linear piezo-elastic constitutive relationship. A series of vibration and impact tests are conducted using the piezo-film sensors connected directly to a voltage measurement device. The measured first three bending frequencies of a cantilever GFRP specimen agree well with the simulated results using a commercial finite element code (MARC), and the difference is less than 5%. It is also observed that if the measured frequency is above 3 kHz, the piezo-film transducer can closely detect the dynamic response of structures without using a charge amplifier. However, the voltage directly measured from piezo-film sensor seems underestimate the structure response at a frequency lower than 3 kHz. Therefore, a modified sensor equation for piezo-film is proposed for lower frequency measurement. Furthermore, drop tests are also performed for the clamped-clamped $[(0/90)_4]_s$ GFRP laminate and 2024 aluminum target. An array of nine piezo-film sensors are glued on the distal surface of specimen to determine the impact response. Transient central deflection of plate is identified based on test finding and the plate-type sensor equation, and the result is found to be in good agreement with the numerical solution using the finite element code (MARC).

1. INTRODUCTION

Using piezoelectric materials to detect structural response have been well known⁽¹⁻³⁾. Recently, extensive studies on using the polyvinylidene-fluoride (PVDF) polymer films and piezo-ceramic elements as sensors/actuators have been extensively reported⁽⁴⁻⁹⁾. Because of the flexibility and ease of use for complicated geometry, these make piezo-film applicable for the development of smart structures. Campbell, et al.⁽¹⁰⁾ showed that piezo-film can be served as an adequate transducer when used for (a) cyclic history monitoring of composite structures if the cyclic loading is greater than 1 Hz and (b) transient and impact response sensing. They also reported that it is not necessary to use the charge amplifiers during tests for above applications. This could provide us a lower-cost and light-weight measurement system to use piezo-film transducers for developing smart structures.

Sensors (e.g. strain gage and piezo-electric transducer) in conjunction with their associated sensor equations are used to determine structural response, and the measurement accuracy could be verified by comparing test finding with the simulated result based on a proper analytical model or finite element code. Previously reported work⁽⁸⁻¹⁰⁾ showed that the piezo-ceramic and piezo-film transducers are able to detect the vibration frequencies of structures closely. However, it seems not clear that whether or not an appropriate sensor equation can accurately predict the measured voltage of piezo-film transducers without using the charge amplifier, when the structure is subject to dynamic loading.

As we know that piezo-film has its inherent nature as a capacitance-type sensor which may be sensitive to the frequency of applied vibration below and above the mid-band rang⁽¹¹⁾. Furthermore, the sensor equation in general is not formulated to be depend upon the frequencies of measured signals. This will not be a problem if we use the resistance-type strain gage, when the measurement is carry out under a

steady environmental condition. But if the capacitance-type transducers (such as the piezo-film sensors) are used, it would be interesting to study the effect of frequency on the measured signals.

Therefore, it seems important to check the accuracy of measured voltage of piezo-film sensors mounted on a structure subject to vibration and impact loading when charge amplifiers are not used. If the measured sensor's output voltage can be closely predicted by the sensor equation for specific structural response. We may then rely on the measured result to determine structural dynamic response based on an appropriate sensor equation. In this work, a series of tests are conducted to characterize the piezo-film sensor for direct vibration and impact response measurement.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND DESCRIPTIONS

In the current work, we use the thin piezo-film sheet (KYNAR) cut to a size of 10 mm x 10 mm x 0.11 mm to make piezo-electric sensors for measuring the structural dynamic response. A summary of the material properties for the piezo-film (PVDF) sensor is tabulated in Table 1. Piezo-film sensor is glued on the surface of the cross-ply cantilever plate made of s-glass/epoxy pre-preg (Fiberite, Hy-E 9134B), and the sensor is placed 100 or 150 mm from the clamped end. A shaker system (LDS, V201) along with the associated power supply and function generator are used to excite specimen's bending vibration modes. Piezo-film transducer is used to detect the structural vibration response, and it is directly connected to the voltage measurement devices - dynamic signal analyzer (HP, 3567). In addition, a resistance-type strain gage (TML, FLA-5-11) is also placed at the same place where the piezo-film sensor is mounted but on the opposite surface of the cantilever composite plate. Strain gage and the associated conditional amplifier (Measurement Group, 2311) are also used to detect the corresponding dynamic response of structure. The geometry of the GFRP cantilever specimen and the locations of piezo-film sensor and strain gage are shown in Figure 1. Tables 2 shows the mechanical properties of s-glass/epoxy laminate (Fiberite, Hy-E 9134B) and the 2024 aluminum specimen. In addition, an impact hammer (B&K, 8202) is also used in order to study the structural transient response. A schematic drawing of the test setup for impact hammer and vibration tests is presented in Figure 2. Signals detected by the strain gage and piezo-film sensor are fed into two separate channels of a dynamic signal analyzer for further analysis. The deflection of test specimen is also determined by using an optofollower (NASA, 1000). This non-contact electro-optical displacement tracer is designed to measure the dynamic response of structures with a frequency upto 300 KHz (flat).

Moreover, the drop-weight tests are also performed to examine the low-speed impact response of the 1.9 mm thick square $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4]_S$ laminate and 2.0 mm thick 2024 aluminum plate. The 60 mm x 60 mm rectangular specimens is rigidly clamped along boundaries and the schematic drawing of impact test setup is shown in Figure 3. Hemispherical tip-ended rod (weighing 36 gm) made of high strength steel with a diameter and length of 12.6 mm and 38.2 mm is used as the impactor. The composite (or aluminum) specimen is struck by the impactor at a velocity of 615 mm/sec (or 542.2 mm/sec). An array of 3 x 3 (nine) piezo-film sensors are placed on the distal surface of the specimen and each sensor is equally spaced on the target. The size of each piezo-film sensor is 10 mm x 10 mm x 0.11 mm. The transient signals detected by these sensors are used to identify the plate central deflection based on the proposed plate-type sensor equation in order to check against the numerical solutions by using the finite element program (MARC).

3. SENSOR EQUATION

Based on the linear theory of piezoelectricity⁽²⁾, the constitutive equations for piezo-film can be expressed as

$$T_p = C_{pq}^E S_q + e_{ip} E_i \quad (1a)$$

$$D_i = e_{iq} S_q + \epsilon_{ik}^S E_k \quad (i, k = 1, 2, 3) \quad (1b)$$

or

$$S_p = S_{pq}^E T_q - d_{ip} E_i \quad (p, q = 1, 2, \dots, 6) \quad (2a)$$

$$D_i = d_{iq} T_q + \epsilon_{ik}^T E_k \quad (2b)$$

where subscripts 1, 2 and 3 (or x, y, z) correspond to the material principal directions. The strain and stress component are represented by S_q and T_p . In addition, D_i , E_k , S_{pq}^E and C_{pq}^E are the component of electric displacement, electric field intensity, compliance matrix and stiffness matrix, respectively. The dielectric constants at constant stress and constant strain are denoted by ϵ_{ik}^T and ϵ_{ik}^S , respectively.

Moreover, e_{ip} and d_{ip} are piezoelectric constants. Notice that the component e_{iq} is equivalent to $d_{ip}C_{pq}^E$. Due to the symmetry property of the piezo film (PVDF)⁽⁷⁾, with the poling axis is the 3 (or z) axis, the piezoelectric constants d_{ip} and dielectric constants ϵ_{ik}^T for piezo film can be simplified to

$$d_{ip} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & d_{15} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & d_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ d_{31} & d_{32} & d_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } \epsilon_{ik}^S = \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11}^S & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \epsilon_{22}^S & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \epsilon_{33}^S \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The electric field-electric potential (ϕ) relations is

$$\phi_{,i}(x, y, z, t) = E_i(x, y, z, t) \quad (4)$$

where $(\cdot)_{,i}$ represents the partial derivative with respect to i index, and let's assume that the electric potential can be express as

$$\phi(x, y, z, t) = z^2 \phi_2(x, y, t) \quad (5)$$

From the classical plate theory, the displacement components for piezo film sensor are

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z, t) &= -z \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}, \\ v(x, y, z, t) &= -z \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \\ w(x, y, z, t) &= w(x, y, t), \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where u , v , and w are the displacement along the x , y and z direction of plate. The charge equation of electrostatics implies

$$\begin{aligned} D_{,i} &= D_{1,1} + D_{2,2} + D_{3,3} = -e_{31} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} - e_{32} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - 2\epsilon_{33} \phi_2 \\ &\quad - z^2 (\epsilon_{11} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_2}{\partial x^2} - \epsilon_{22} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_2}{\partial y^2}) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Notice that the variable z represents the position along the transverse direction of plate and is arbitrary. If we neglect the higher order term in above equation for a simple plate theory, we may obtain an expression for ϕ_2 in terms of the transverse displacement (w) as

$$\phi_2(x, y, t) = -\frac{1}{2\epsilon_{33}} \left[e_{31} \frac{\partial^2 w(x, y, t)}{\partial x^2} + e_{32} \frac{\partial^2 w(x, y, t)}{\partial y^2} \right] \quad (8)$$

Equation (7) is the approximated plate-type sensor equation for piezo film. After substitute equation (7) into (4), the output voltage (i.e. $V_{out}(x, y, t)$) of piezo film can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} V_{out}(x, y, t) &= \phi(x, y, z_b, t) - \phi(x, y, z_a, t) = (z_b^2 - z_a^2) \phi_2(x, y, t) \\ &= -\frac{(z_b^2 - z_a^2)}{2\epsilon_{33}} \left[e_{31} \frac{\partial^2 w(x, y, t)}{\partial x^2} + e_{32} \frac{\partial^2 w(x, y, t)}{\partial y^2} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where z_a and z_b are the coordinates of piezo-film's electrodes as shown in Figure 1. Equation (9) is the plate-type sensor equation for piezoelectric transducers. We may reduce equation (9) to the familiar beam-type sensor equation by dropping the dependency of y variable and obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
V_{out}(x,t) &= -\frac{e_{31}}{2\epsilon_{33}}(z_b^2 - z_a^2) \frac{\partial^2 w(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \\
&\approx -\frac{1}{2} g_{31} t_s (t_s + t_b) E_s \frac{\partial^2 w(x,t)}{\partial x^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where t_b and t_s correspond to the thickness of beam and piezo film, respectively. The elastic modulus of piezo-film is represented by E_s . The relation $(e_{31}/\epsilon_{33}) = [(d_{31}E_s)/\epsilon_{33}] = (g_{31}E_s)$ has been used above to relate the output voltage of piezo film to the piezoelectric stress constant (g_{31}). Notice that the derived sensor equation (10) do not depend upon the signal's frequency. If this sensor equation is adequate for structure dynamic measurement, we should be able to predict the measured sensor voltage for given structural response at the sensor's location. Conversely, the structural response can be identified when the measured sensor voltage is measured. However, in general such piezoelectric transducer as a capacitance-type sensor is sensitive to the frequency of applied vibration below and above the mid-band range⁽¹¹⁾. Therefore, it seems important to examine the dependency of frequency on the piezo-sensor equation (10) when structure is subject to dynamic loading.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Vibration tests of $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{4S}$ laminated cantilever plates (250 mm x 80 mm x 1.9 mm) are performed. The piezo-film sensor is mounted on the specimen (150 mm from the clamped end) and is connected directly to a dynamic signal analyzer in order to examine vibration frequencies. The measured first three bending frequencies are found to be 22.52, 142.2, and 378.7 Hz based on the averaged values of three measurements for each frequency. A finite element code (MARC) is used to compute the structural vibration frequencies and the simulated results are shown in Table 3. This table reveals that the difference between the test results and code simulations is within 5%. It means that the piezo-film sensor can closely determine the structural vibration frequencies. During the test, an optofollower is also used to track the deflection of the specimen at sensor's location. Based on the measured deflection corresponding to a specific mode, we can determine the structural deformation profile and predict the sensor's voltage based on the sensor equation (10). A summary the measured and predicted voltages of piezo-films is shown in Table 4, when the piezo-film sensors are placed 150 mm away from the clamped end. Table 4 also shows the result when piezo-film sensor is place at a distance 100 mm away from the clamped end. This table reveals that the measured voltage significantly underestimate the predicted values. This discrepancy suggests that a detail characterization of the piezo-film sensor for measuring vibration response is needed.

In order to examine the difference between the measured and computed voltage mentioned in the previous paragraph, piezo film transducer and strain gage are placed on the specimen's frontal and distal surfaces at a position 150 cm away from the clamped end. We perform the impact hammer test for the GFRP specimen and analyze the signals detected from piezo film and strain gage using dynamic signal analyzer. Notice that the piezo film's signal is directly fed into the analyzer, while the strain gage's signal is amplified by a signal conditioner and then fed into another channel the analyzer. A plots of the voltage ratio of these two signals versus frequencies is shown in Figure 4. A mean voltage ratio of 12.2 dB (dB = $20 \log[\text{voltage of PVDF}/\text{voltage of strain gage}]$) with the standard deviation of 2.1 dB is calculated, based on the curve shown in this Figure for a frequency ranging from 3 to 10 KHz. Notice that when the frequency is below 3 KHz, the voltage ratio deviates from this mean value. Because the capacitance type sensors are sensitive to the frequency of applied vibration loading.

According to the theory of strain gage, we could write down the sensor equations for strain gages as

$$V_{s.g.} = V_{br} A \frac{K}{4} \epsilon = -V_{br} A \frac{K}{4} z_a \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \tag{11}$$

where K is the gage factor for strain gage. Parameters V_{br} and A are the excitation voltage and gain of the signal conditioner, respectively. From equations (10) and (11), the voltage ratio of these two signals (i.e. $V_{pvdf}/V_{s.g.}$) can be expressed as

$$\frac{V_{pvdf}}{V_{s.g.}} = \left[\frac{2}{V_{BR} A K} \frac{e_{31}}{\epsilon_{33}} \frac{(z_b^2 - z_a^2)}{z_a} \right] \tag{12}$$

The bracket term shown above is related to the signal conditioner's setting, the sensors' location, and the

material properties of piezo-film. For the current tests, the parameters K , A and V_{br} are 2.12, 1000, and 15 volts, respectively. After we substitute the parameters' value to equation (12), the voltage ratio ($V_{pvd}/V_{s.g.}$) is calculated to be 4.3 (or 12.67 dB) for composite specimen. The difference between this calculated value 4.3 (12.67 dB) and the test mean value 4.1 (12.2 dB) is within 5 % for the frequency ranging from 3 to 10 KHz. This result suggests that the sensor equation for piezo-film can closely predict the measured voltage of piezo-film sensor in this frequency range. However, if the frequency is less than 3 KHz, the piezo-film sensor equation seems unable to predict the measured voltage of piezo-film sensor closely. Therefore, it is concluded that sensor equation needs to be calibrated for lower frequency range in order to take into account this discrepancy.

In addition, we also performed the impact hammer test on an aluminum cantilever plate (200 mm x 80 mm x 2.0 mm). The test condition is the same as we conduct the test for composite specimen described above except that the piezo-film sensor is placed 120 mm away from the clamped end. Again, it shows that for a frequency ranging from 3 to 10 KHz, the mean voltage ratio is determined to be 12.5 dB (with a standard deviation of 1.1 dB) based on the test result, and this value is close to the predicted value (i.e. 12.64 dB) based on the equation (12). Similar to that found for the GFRP laminated specimen, a deviation from the predicted value also occurs when the frequency is below 3 KHz. This reveals that the effect of frequency on the measured voltage for a piezo-film sensor in the lower frequency range (i.e. less than 3 KHz) exists and this effect seems not to be depend upon whether the piezo-film sensors are mounted on aluminum plate or GFRP laminated specimen.

Therefore, we introduce the following modified sensor equation to relate the measured voltage (V_{pvd}) and the structure dynamic response (w) for piezo-film transducer without using the charge amplifier as

$$V_{pvd} = -GF(\omega) \frac{e_{31}}{2e_{33}} (z_b^2 - z_a^2) \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \quad (13)$$

where $GF(\omega)$ is defined as the gain function for piezo-film transducer and ω is the frequency. Based on the test result found above, the gain function (i.e. $GF(\omega)$) is set to unity when the frequency is above 3 KHz. From equations (11) and (13), we can obtain an expression of the corrected voltage ratio for these two signals (i.e. $V_{pvd}/V_{s.g.}$) as

$$\frac{V_{pvd}}{V_{s.g.}} = GF(\omega) \left[\frac{2}{V_{BR}AK} \frac{e_{31}}{e_{33}} \frac{(z_b^2 - z_a^2)}{z_a} \right] \quad (14)$$

The gain function for piezo-film sensor shown in above equation may be identified based on the test result described in the next paragraph, and is used to correct the signal directly measured from the piezo-film without using a charge amplifier for a frequency less than 3 KHz.

As we know that the narrower frequency span can provide us with greater frequency resolution. Therefore, we perform the impact hammer test to sample the signal at a narrower frequency span. A plot of the ratio of the measured voltage of piezo film and strain gage versus the frequency sampled in a frequency span of dc to 1.6 KHz for GFRP laminated specimen subject to impact hammer loading is shown in Figure 5. In addition, we also conduct the sweep sine tests to examine the voltage ratio for the composite specimen excited in the range of dc to 1 KHz and the corresponding frequency response is shown in the Figure 6. Examining Figures 4 to 6 reveals that measured voltage ratio is depend upon frequencies. Moreover, additional vibration and impact hammer tests are conducted when the piezo film and strain gage are mounted on a different location. Similar characteristics is also observed and the effect of the sensor's location on the measured voltage ratio seems limited. Based on the test results shown in Figures 4 to 6, a curve fitting process utilizing the 10th order Chebyshev polynomial is adopted to identify the gain function $GF(\omega)$ for piezo-film sensor. The relationship of gain factor versus the frequency is plotted in Figure 7. Curves A and B represent the fitted gain functions when the piezo-film sensors are placed on the 2.0 mm thick aluminum plate and 1.9 mm thick cross-ply GFRP laminates, respectively. In addition, the circular (or cross) points shown in this Figure represent the measured voltage ratio versus calculated result base on equation (10) for the first three vibration frequencies of the cross-ply GFRP laminate when piezo-film sensor is mounted 150 mm (or 100 mm) away from the clamped end. The value corresponding to each data points shown in this Figure is tabulated in the Table 4. The difference between the data points and the fitted curve at each vibration frequency is limited. This conclude that this calibration process is proper for lower frequency measurement if the piezo-film sensor is used directly to detect the dynamic response of structure without utilizing the charge amplification device.

Moreover, the drop tests of 60 cm x 60 cm $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4]_S$ laminate (1.9 mm thick) and 2024 aluminum plate (2.0 mm thick) are also conducted. The impact response is detected by an array of nine piezo-film sensors installed on the distal surface of target. A hemispherical tip-ended cylindrical impactor weighing 36 gm is fired against the composite specimen and aluminum target with an impact velocity of 65 mm/sec and 542.2 mm/sec, respectively. Figure 3 shows the impact test setup and the location of piezo-film sensors. These sensors are connected separately to digital oscilloscopes using a total of nine channels to record the transient response. Based on the plate sensor equation (9) and the finite difference technique, we may identify the central transient deflection of target. A more detail description of the identification process is referred to reference (12). The circular points shown in Figure 8 represent the identified central deflection of the cross-ply composite specimen subject to impact loading. The target's transient central deflection is also computed by using a finite element code (MARC) based on traditional thick plate element without considering the piezo-electric effect. It shows that the identified result resemble the code simulated result. In addition, Figure 9 shows a similar result for aluminum specimen struck the impactor. This concluded that it is adequate to use the piezo-film sensor directly for detecting the response of target subject to impact loading.

CONCLUSIONS

A series of tests are performed to characterize the piezo-film for direct vibration and low-speed impact response measurement. Both $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4]_S$ GFRP laminate and 2024 aluminum plate are used as specimens. It is concluded that the piezo-film sensor can closely predict the first three bending frequencies. When the frequency is less than 3 kHz, the measured voltage under-estimate the structure response. A modified sensor equation is proposed in account for this discrepancy and the corresponding gain function is used to calibrate the voltage directly measured from piezo-film transducer. For a higher frequency ranging from 3 kHz to 10 kHz, piezo-film sensor can closely predict the structure response without using a charge amplification device. An array of nine piezo-film transducers are used directly to identify the target central transient deflection based on the plate-type sensor equation. The identified impact response is found to be in good agreement with the simulated result by using a finite element code (MARC) for the cross-ply GFRP laminate and aluminum specimen.

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Figure 1 The geometry of GFRP laminated specimen and the locations of piezo-film sensors and strain gage.

Figure 2 The schematic drawing of vibration and impact hammer tests setup.

Figure 3 A schematic drawing of the low-speed drop test using an array of nine piezo-film sensors to detect impact response of the cross-ply GFRP laminate and aluminum specimen..

Figure 4 A plot of the ratio of the measured voltage of the piezo-electric sensors and strain gage versus frequencies for cross-ply GFRP specimen struck by an impact hammer.

Figure 5 A plot of the ratio of measured voltage ratio for piezo-film sensor and strain gage versus frequencies for GFRP laminated specimen with a frequency span of dc - 1.6 kHz.

Figure 6 A plot of the ratio of measured voltage ratio for piezo-film sensor and strain gage versus frequencies from sweep sine vibration test for GFRP laminated specimen with a frequency span of dc - 1.0 kHz.

Figure 7 A plot of the gain factor versus frequencies. The curves A and B represent the fitted results for aluminum specimen and cross-ply GFRP specimen, respectively. The circular and cross points shown above corresponding to the first three bending modes for cross-ply GFRP laminates when sensors are placed 100 mm and 150 mm from the clamped end.

Figure 8 A plot of the central deflection of cross-ply GFRP laminate versus time, when target is struck by an impactor at a velocity of 615 mm/sec.

Figure 9 A plot of the central deflection of aluminum plate versus time, when target is struck by an impactor at a velocity of 542.2 mm/sec.

Table 1 Material properties used in calculation for KYNAR piezo-film (PVDF)

E_S	2.0 GPa	d_{15}	23×10^{-12} m/V
ρ	1780 Kg/m^3	d_{24}	23×10^{-12} m/V
ν	0.29	ϵ_{11}	-106.2×10^{-12} Farad/m
d_{31}	23×10^{-12} m/V	ϵ_{22}	-106.2×10^{-12} Farad/m
d_{32}	3×10^{-12} m/V	ϵ_{33}	-106.2×10^{-12} Farad/m
d_{33}	-33×10^{-12} m/V		

Table 2 Mechanical properties of the s-glass/ epoxy laminates (Fiberite Hy-E 9134B) and aluminum sample.

s-glass/epoxy [0°] laminate		aluminum alloy (2024)	
E_1	56.52 GPa	E	72.32 GPa
E_2	18.94 GPa	ν	0.33
G_{12}	7.729 GPa	ρ	$2,764 \text{ Kg/m}^3$
ν_{12}	0.265		
ρ	1881 Kg/m^3		

Table 3 The measure and computed vibration frequencies of $[(0^\circ/90^\circ)_4]_S$ laminate.

vibration mode	test results (Hz)	MARC computed results (Hz)
1st (B)*	22.52	21.43
2nd (T)	-	100.29
3rd (B)	141.2	134.18
4th (B+T)	-	323.37
5th (B)	378.7	375.75

* the symbol B and T in the bracket represent the bending and torsion mode, respectively.

Table 4 Computed and measured peak piezo-film voltage corresponding to the first three bending modes of cross-ply GFRP laminate

	1st bending mode	2nd bending mode	3rd bending mode	note
measured result (mV)	60.75	253	203	sensor are placed 100 mm away from the clamped end
calculated result (mV)	2,893	1,921	605	
ratio	0.0209	0.132	0.336	
measured result (mV)	38.25	307	239	sensor are placed 150 mm away from the clamped end
calculated result (mV)	1,459	2,243	670	
ratio	0.0262	0.137	0.357	

* the measured displacement at sensor's location and sensor equation (10a) are used to determine the calculated result above.